

TEACHER - EVALUATION TOOLS AND THE RESULTS-BASED PERFORMANCE OF CLASSROOM LEADERS IN TIAONG I DISTRICT, DIVISION OF QUEZON

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ABSTRACT

The study attempted to determine the relationship of teacher-evaluation tools and the results-based performance of classroom leaders working in the public elementary schools of Tiaong I District. The respondents of the study were two hundred (200) elementary school teachers in Tiaong I District, Division of Quezon. The study made use of the quantitative method of research utilizing survey research design. The study revealed the following findings: The perception of classroom leaders' on the different types of control system is always observed in the teacher-evaluation tools. The classroom leaders' perceived that the different types of clinical supervision are always observed in the teacher-evaluation tools. The Individual Performance-based Commitment and Review or IPCRF has a significant relationship to the teacher's performance. Based on the above findings, the following conclusions are drawn: The hypothesis stating that the classroom leaders' performance is not significantly related to the types of teacher-evaluation tools is therefore rejected. In light of the foregoing findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are respectfully endorsed: Since the control system in terms of input is significantly related to the teacher-evaluation tools, it is recommended that all teachers should be permitted to pursue graduate studies, attend conferences, seminars and workshops. It is also recommended that teachers should be given feedback with realistic appraisal during classroom observation, so that teachers will give positive work response. Since the KRAs in the Individual Performance-based Commitment and Review Form are significantly related to the teacher-evaluation tools, it is recommended that it will be adjusted to the New Normal Situation. A follow-up study parallel to this one maybe conducted with the inclusion of other variables like the one applicable for the New Normal setting such as Modular Distance Learning, Online Distance Learning, and Television/Radio Based Instruction to enhance this research further.

Keywords: Control system, clinical supervision, classroom-leaders' performance